

Women Characters in Manju Kapur's *Difficult Daughters*: A Study

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: September

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-2645

Impact Factor: 4.110

Citation:

Leelavathi, R. "Women Characters in Manju Kapur's *Difficult Daughters*: A Study." *Shanlax International Journal of English*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 37-40.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3461753>

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Abstract

The article is about the evolution in the portrayal of women in Indian English Novels written by Manju Kapur. The aims of the article to show how the women characters portrayed in the novels the past three decades reflect the changes that are taking place in Indian society. There is a lot of differences in the way women portrayed-their desires, their trauma as presented in the novels of Manju Kapur. She tries to show the gradual change in the outlook of the character as well as the change in the social outlook through the novels of Manju Kapur. It gives the changing of scenes and life style of women, trying to contrast it with the pre-independent period and earlier and eventually. The writer shows how women realize that they have been suppressed and exploited and they register the protest. The struggle to cope up with situations results either in depression or in protest leading to marital disharmony and family integration. It further focuses on desire for freedom results in conflicts within the individual about sticking on to the traditional outline and fulfilment of one's desires violating some of the traditional forms and the second one being the individual in conflict with the society. The article analyses the women characters and focuses on their search for identity, there by establishing the change in perception in their outlook.

Keywords: Changing outlook of women's life, individual conflict, searching for identity.

Women are often the subject of literary works, seen as an object to Behold of an earthly link to God, however, in the works of early British Literature, the image of women ranged from political peace Keeper to anti-beauty in the Old English tradition, women are seen as either dutiful slaves or angelic creatures from heaven, According to the history, the women of the household or kingdom serviced her husband and the men of the table as the consummate hostess, keeping quit and keeping the drink poured.

But Manju Kapur's as a feminist writer covering all her five novels. The novel explains unquestionable ability to travel around the consciousness of the modern day urban, educated middle-class. The protagonists are trapped in the midway between tradition and modernity. It is an attempt to study Kapur's women protagonists, as portrayed by her in her novels, with a view to understand and appreciate their trials and tribulations under the impact of the conflicting influence of tradition and modernity. And also it is critically analyze their response to the budding situation in life so as

to fit themselves in the modern society. The fictional works of Kapur shows both daring and desires of the Indian women in the fictional works Kapur.

Maniu Kapur born in 1948 in the city of Amritsar. She is a daughter of veteran educationist Raghuvansha Kishore Kapur, who was Vice Chancellor 'of Sambalpur University. She is completed her B. A. Honours in English literature from Miranda House University College for Women at Delhi. Then she is gone to Canada to take her M.A. in English at Dalhousie University in Halifax, Nova Scotia. After completing her M. Phil. at Delhi University, she joined her alma mater Miranda House College as a lecturer in English. After teaching English Literature for almost 30 years, she takes voluntary retirement from her service. Now is a fulltime writer. She is married to a Delhi based industrialist named Gun Nidhi Dalmia and lives in Delhi.

Kapur's first novel, *Difficult Daughters* which is received an international acclaimed novel. *Difficult Daughters* is partially based on the life of her mother Virmathi's life. It is a story of three generation women. Ida is the narrator of the story who is the daughter of Virmathi, the protagonist of the novel. In this novel Ida narrates the struggle of her mother Virmathi. Virmathi's mother Kasturi is an ever-pregnant lady, who has eleven children. Though Virmathi is a sister but she lives as mother of them. She helps to her mother in every pregnancy. In *Difficult Daughters*, Manju Kapur is not only focus Virmathi, but also her feelings. She deals number of other women characters and how they can fight for their freedom. Not only fight for their freedom, but also participate actively in the political activities. *Difficult Daughters* is a painful story of a sensitive girl who struggle the male-dominated society.

In *Difficult Daughters*, Manju Kapur deals three generation of women. The first generation women are Kasturi and Ganga. Kasturi is a traditional woman. On the time of partition educated girls only gets a well educated bridegroom. So she is gone to school to get educated bridegroom. In her mother's house she learns reading, writing balancing household accounts and sewing. She spends his whole life to obey others. She doesn't ask any question against her husband, because she obeys the traditional rules. Her life is trapped in the patriarchal world around her. Motherhood is one such trap. She has give eleven children. Life become burden in her every pregnancies. Her repeated pregnancies made her very sick. Ruby Milhoutra observes that,

"Kasturi's repeated pregnancies made her sickly, resulting in her total dependence on Virmati to manage her household. As a natural consequence her unique position in the home is lost which she has to yield to her daughter quite unwillingly. Virmati thus becomes a 'substitute' and not the double' that every mother wants her daughter to be. As a consequence the relationship assumes hostile dimensions." (165)

Ganga is the traditional women. She is an uneducated woman, but she gets married with the educated man who is worked as a professor in the oxford university. The professor doesn't like his wife for her being uneducated. He tries to teach her reading and writing. But she does not show any interest to learn reading and writing. So he doesn't like uneducated woman. As Ganga's character sketch moves forward it becomes clear that Kapur through Ganga gives her readers a glimpse of the process of growing up as a girl in India. Her husband continues to be her public statement of selfhood. Even after the professor's second marriage Ganga continues her routine with her bindi and her bangles, her toe rings and her mangalsutra and it all suggests that she still considers him as her god.

After the second marriage of the professor, Ganga doesn't stop her routine work. Because in Indian tradition husband is like god. To be a house wife is sometimes a curse in India. Women that do not have out to work are always devalued. Afraid to get out of family relationships they are literally trapped in their own family. The professor's wife, Ganga is one such example. She prays to God everyday that her house should be free from evil; outside influences till her children were

grown up and settled. Then she would resign herself to whatever was in store for her. When her husband remarries, it is as if her life is over but rebellion or opposition is not an option that is open to her. She accepts it as her fate.

Virmati is a second generation woman. From her novel, *Difficult Daughters* depicts the inner and the outer world of its female lead, Virmati and her fatigue for life. This novel deals Virmati's life is ragged among her responsibility of family, thirst of education and also deals the illicit love with the professor, who is already married. Virmati is born. She is a sensitive young girl. She is the elder daughter of Kasturi and Suraj Prakash. They have eleven children. She undertakes her home, when she is seventeen. She goes to Dalhousie with her mother Kasturi, to look after her. In Dalhousie Virmati meets her cousin Shakuntala, who is studying in Lahore. She is deeply impressed by Shakuntala's glamorous, vibrant and intelligent personality. Virmati wants to live independent life like Shakuntala and she dreams of the glamorous life of metropolitan life. So she joins AS college in Lahore for higher studies. In this college she meets the professor and fall in love with the professor. Due to the relationship with the professor she stopped her marriage. She goes to RBSL College to her higher studies. Here she gets pregnancy and it is aborted with the help of her roommate. She gets married to the professor on the way to Shanthi Niketan. But the professor is already a married man. So Virmati's family members don't accept the marriage. She gets pregnancy and gives birth to a girl child. The professor gives a name to his girl child "Ida". Ida means a new beginning.

Ida, Virmati's only daughter represents the third generation of women and she is the narrator of this novel. She is portrayed as a radical woman of contemporary India. She refuses to submit the dictates of male dominant society and believes in personal freedom. Her father wants her to look pretty, neat, well-dressed and he also likes her to study well, learn classical music, and take dance lessons, and so on. But she is not at all interested in studies. And when her mother complains, "You mean living only by yourself. You are disappointing your father" (DD 279). She rudely retorts "Why is it so important to please him" (DD 279). She doesn't care for her parents' desires. She gives importance only to gratify her own wishes. Surendra Narayan Jha rightly comments,

Ida was not at all interested in displaying any signs of intellectual brightness. Rather her prime concern always spelled out the youthful frivolity merely. She hardly ever intended to be worthy of her parents expectations. Only her own self mattered most for her. (221)

Ida is introduced in the novel as a divorcee. "I know my relatives feel sorry for me. I am without husband, child, or parents. I can see the ancient wheels of my divorce still grinding and clanking in their heads" (DD 4). All parents expect their daughters to get married to an educated and respectful man. Similarly, Ida's parents Harish and Virmati hunt for an ideal bride groom, and their choice is Prabhakar- "He was a successful academic, a writer of books, a connoisseur of culture, a disseminator of knowledge" (DD 157). And so, Ida is wedded to Prabhakar. But her conjugal life with Prabhakar is not happy and pleasant as they thought, rather it turns into a disastrous marriage. She suffers a lot being trapped in a loveless marriage. Her husband never shows any sign of love towards her. When she informs him that she becomes pregnant, he mercilessly asks her to abort the child. She is shocked at his words and is completely broken. Yet as a stoic woman, she never shares it to her mother. She states,

Now I have nothing. Mother, I never told you this, because you thought Prabhakar was so wonderful, and I was glad that in the choice of husband I had pleased you. Why should I burden you with my heartaches when you had enough of your own? (DD 156-157)

This proves that Ida is a stoic woman. She obliges her loveless husband's words and gets it aborted. Thus, she suffers in the hands of insensitive, irresponsible and inhuman husband. Joya Chakravarthy says, Ida is "strong and clearheaded" (98). Denial of maternity and forced abortion

prepares her mentally to break up the relationship with her husband. She has the strength which Virmati lacks, and as such she frees herself from the tormenting husband. Ida's life becomes miserable, when she gets divorce from her husband and stays single. She leads her life all alone. The epilogue mirrors her pathetic condition of life.

I was nothing, husbandless, childless. I felt myself hovering like a pencil notation on the margins of society. For long periods I was engulfed in melancholy, depression, and despair. I would lie in bed for hours, unable to sleep, pitying myself for all I didn't have, blaming my mother, myself. (DD 279)

Thus, Manju Kapur beautifully and brilliantly propagates different alternatives in the traditional and conventional way of life. She is of view that the traditional concept of marriage and man-woman relationship has become outdated and it must be re-defined and re-shaped. Almost all her novels have justified this attitude with microscopic observations. Almost all her novels have justified this attitude with microscopic observations. The portrayal of women in Indian English fiction as the silent victim and upholder of the tradition and traditional values of family and society has undergone a tremendous change and is no longer presented as a passive character.

Works Cited

1. Chakravarty, Joya. "A Study of Difficult Daughters and A Married Woman." *Indian Women Novelists in English*. Ed. Jaydipsinh Dodiya. New Delhi: Sarup & Sons. 2006. 201- 207. Print.
2. Kapur, Manju. *Difficult Daughters*. London: Faber and Faber, 1998. Print.
3. Rohidas Nitonde. Dr. *In Search of Feminist Writer*. India. Partridge. 2014. Print.
4. Jha, Surendra Narayan. "The Treatment of Modern Women in Indian English Novel and Manju Kapur's Difficult Daughters". *Reflections of Indian English Literature*. New Delhi: Atlantic Publishers. 2002. Print.